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N-Power Programme, Poverty Alleviation And Socio-economic Development In The Niger Delta

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ABSTRACT

The N-Power Programme, established by the Nigerian government, aims to address youth unemployment, reduce poverty, and foster socio-economic development in the Niger Delta region. This initiative provides opportunities for young graduates and non-graduates through skills training, job placement, and financial support. Evaluating the impact of the N-Power Programme in the Niger Delta reveals significant benefits for participants, including enhanced employability, increased income, and improved living standards. Adopting the Elite theory and a systems approach as its theoretical framework, the research employed a survey design that gathered both primary data (through questionnaires and interviews) and secondary data. Data analysis involved simple percentage methods. The finding of the paper indicate that there is lack of adequate data, among others. Based on the above, the paper recommends among others that State and local governments should provide accurate data of those living in poverty while the federal government coordinate, oversee and monitor poverty alleviation programmes in the Niger Delta region.

Keywords: Poverty alleviation, development, Niger Delta, N-Power programme, and socio-economic development

INTRODUCTION

The federal government initiated the N-Power scheme in 2016 to tackle poverty and unemployment in order to achieve its desire purpose in the Niger Delta and Nigeria in general (N-Power, 2017). The government also recognizes the fact that education is the bedrock of development in any society and, thus introduced the N-Power programme, to enhance the learning capacity of younger students and advance socioeconomic development through the N-Teach component while it (government) provides computing devices to digitalize the scheme (Akujuru and Enyioko, 2019). However, the programme has been fraught with poor stipend, irregular payment, and other forms of official recklessness while acute lateness, unauthorised absenteeism and other forms of truancy are also reported against volunteers.

The N-Agro component which was meant to function as intermediary between research and farmers, operates as facilitators and communicators, helping farmers in their decision-making and ensuring that appropriate knowledge is implemented to obtain the best results on farms. The programme appears to be semi-autonomous and focuses on small farm owners also adopts the integrated rural development strategy in its operations. The N-Power Health programme on the other hand ensures that volunteers are trained to work as public health assistants. They teach preventive health to community members including pregnant women, children, families and individuals. They are also trained to provide basic diagnostic services (FG, 2020).

Despite all these commitments from the government, the successes recorded in N-Agro and N-Health components continue to face wanton challenges which occurred in the course of executing these projects. The challenges include shortage of fund, limited involvement of input agencies, problem

with counterpart funding, technological transfer issues, absence of competent staff to complement and sustain the roles of volunteers, obscure vision and mission of the programme and provision of facilities required for the projects take off. This made implementation much slower than scheduled.

It is no doubt, the past poverty alleviation programmes such as SAP, NAPEP, SURE-P, and numerous schemes have not achieved the desire objectives (Emejuru, Egobueze, & Davies, 2022). This is perhaps due to the problems identified with the implementation of the programmes. According to Aminu, Abubakar, Jamilu and Muhammed (2018) opine that successive state governments in the Niger Delta have also attempted to alleviate poverty through several poverty alleviation related programmes, but the conclusion is that as laudable as some of these programmes, they have not been able to lift the life of majority of Nigerians especially the Niger Delta people above the poverty line.

Indeed, the programmes have constantly been faced with bad governance, corruption, lack of continuity, weak governance, corruption and mismanagement, lack of involvement of targeted population, excessive political interest, insecurity, among others (Adah and Abasilim, 2015). These have always crippled poverty alleviation programmes which brazenly threatens socioeconomic development in the Niger Delta. For instance, the graduate component of the N-Power programme was also confronted with a deluge of challenges mostly orchestrated by officials or managers of the National Social Investment Management Scheme (NASIMS).

Public outcry exposed the weaknesses of the programme such as poor stipends, delay in payment, lack of sustainability, change of government and policy inconsistency, poor governance/management, ineffective population target, unwieldy scope of the programmes, overlapping of functions which ultimately led to institutional rivalry and conflicts, uncoordinated sectoral policy initiatives, lack of involvement of social partners, inadequate funding, lack of computing devices to vast majority of the volunteer corps, bribery, double placement, lateness to work, acute absenteeism, lack of clear vision, etc. The inability to address the challenges discussed above no doubt has contributed to social problems such as the high rate of poverty, unemployment, starvation, and increased crime rate in the Niger Delta and, thus propelled our ambitions to investigate poverty alleviation programme and socioeconomic development with particular reference to the implementation of the N-Power scheme in the Niger Delta region.

Based on the above, a research question is posed thus: What is the role of the N-Power Programme in promoting human capital development and capacity building among beneficiaries in the Niger Delta?

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The paper adopted the Elite theory, according to Obi, Nwachukwu and Obiora (2008) gained importance in the early twentieth century through the different writings of four sociologists, Vilfredo Pareto (1848-1923), Gaetano Mosca (1858-1941), Robert Michels (1876-1936), Ortega Y. Gasset (1883-1955) and Mills (1956). The theory was adopted by Idakwoji to explain the role of policy makers in the political society. Stephen used the theory to describe the functions and character display in the management of an organization while Obi, Nwachukwu and Obiora adopted the theory in explaining the role of the government (legislature, executive and judiciary) in decision making and implementation. However, Idakwoji noted that the theory was used to create a distinction between the rich and the poor, haves and haves not, government and govern, bourgeois and proletariat, etc. Interestingly, this theory is adopted to identify status of the policy makers, their intentions and describe the behaviour as it concerns implementation. The intrigues involved in the conception of the N-Power programme, the process of implementation and the interaction that existed amongst participants or volunteers, the network and the result or report of the implementation.

They noted that the term “elite” was derived from the French, and it meant something excellent. The theorists believed that the division of any society into two is natural, and it regards competence and aptitude to be responsible for this division (Gaubu, 2003). However, this work adopts the orientation and perception of Mills’ elite theory. Mills assumes that all political power is held by a relatively small and wealthy groups sharing similar values and interests and coming from relatively similar privileged backgrounds. He argued that institutions were structured in such manner that those at the top of institutional hierarchy, monopolizes power (Anonymous, n.d).

The theory stressed that the bulk of the population was pictured as passive and inactive controlled by the power elites, which subjected the instruments to psychic management and manipulations. Salawu

(2023) claimed that elites are ubiquitous, they are the most influential and prestigious stratum in the society. These 'elite' are those people who are recognized as outstanding leaders in a given field. Of course, there are political, economic, scientific, business and artistic elites with which societies in all its strata are moved and shaken. Even in a democratic regime where power is meant to reside in the demos 'the people', power is concentrated in the hands of a few. All political organizations, even democracies tend towards domination by an oligarchy, which Mills (1956) called the power elite; this is the iron law of oligarchy as stated by Michels in 1915. Current elite theory defines elites as actors that control resources, occupy key positions, as well as relate through power networks. The author revealed that elite theory opposes pluralism, a tradition that emphasized how multiple major social groups and interests have an influence upon and various forms of representation within more powerful sets of rulers, contributing to decently representative political outcomes that reflect the collective needs of society.

On their part, Obi, Nwachukwu and Obiora (2008) opined that the basic assumption of the theory is that society consists of two classes; the higher stratum which is the elite and the lower stratum, the non-elite. The elite class is further sub-divided into the governing and non-governing elite. They advanced that the major tenet of elite theory is that major decisions which affect society are considered by elite and these decisions usually reflect the interest of the elite rather than the wishes of the poor masses. Idakwoji asserts that public policy or decisions at any given time may be viewed as the preference and values of the governing elites. Although, we often assert that public policy reflects the demands of the people or masses, this may express the myth rather than the reality in any society. The theory suggests that the masses are apathetic and ill-informed about government programmes and that the elites shape the masses' opinion on policy questions more than the people shape the elite's opinion. Just like Obi, Nwachukwu and Obiora, the author, Idakwoji revealed that elite theory can be summarized thus:

- a. Society is divided into two main classes the "few" who have power and the "many" who do not. These few who have power allocate values for the whole society.
- b. The few who govern are not typical of the masses who are governed. Elites are drawn disproportionately from the upper socio-economic strata of the society.
- c. Only non-elites who have accepted the basic elite consensus can be admitted to governing circles and the movement must be slow to maintain stability and avoid revolution.
- d. Public policy does not reflect demands of the masses but rather the prevailing values of the elites.
- e. Active elites are subject to relatively little direct influence from the apathetic masses.

The implications of the elite model are that changes and innovations in policies and programmes come about as a result of redefinitions of elite values. Secondly, changes in the nature of the political system occur only when events threaten the system, and elites, acting on the basis of enlightened self-interest, institute reforms to preserve the system and their place in it. According to Salawu (2023), despite the beautiful content of the elite theory, it has also been criticized because:

- a. It is culturally relative and symptomatic i.e. it is borne out of bureaucratic and non-democratic culture. The theory is accused of not being empirical. However, some empirical statements on inequality for example were made. Those that are not testable include value commitment to the status quo, stability, political order and domination by the minority.
- b. The theory was rejected for its polemical attack on Marxism. It has to be noted that this attack stems from works of classical theorists that were conscious rejoinders to the central element of Marxist political theory.
- c. Elite theory was criticized for assuming self-consciousness, coherence and unity of the elite group. Elite theories-Pareto and Mosca assume the elite group is homogenous.

In spite of weaknesses, elite theory remains relevant in understanding government's poverty alleviation programmes. Poverty alleviation and socioeconomic development programmes are determined by ruling elites and carried into effect by public bureaucrats. Poverty alleviation and socioeconomic development programmes reflect elites' values and serve their ends. The masses do not influence policy through their demands or actions. Elite theory is provocative because policy is the product of elites, reflecting their values and serving their ends. In the Niger Delta and Nigeria, poverty is caused by bad governance and selfish leadership. Nnadozie (2010) noted that any attempt to address poverty in Nigeria must be zeroed in on the problem of leadership inertia and bad governance. He opined that Nigeria is overwhelmed by poverty today can easily be attributed to poor, visionless, inept and selfish leadership. Poverty in Nigeria is due to poor leadership and governance. The elites in Nigeria are visionless and selfish, leading to poverty. Political elites in Nigeria fail to lead responsibly and prefer to embezzle public funds. The Niger Delta is

economically important but resources are mismanaged by elites. Public funds meant for poverty alleviation are wasted on personal luxuries. This leads to poor implementation of poverty alleviation programs. In light of the above, the study postulates that the N-Power programme was conceived by political elites who control the implementation for personal gain. The elites manipulate public policy and government programmes, diverting funds meant for the poor in the Niger Delta. They deceive the masses with seemingly beneficial programs, but use corrupt methods to embezzle public funds. The Batch C2 of N-Power volunteers are owed 8 months stipends despite programme ending in October 2023. N-Power beneficiaries were not paid on time. Minister of humanitarian affairs, Dr. Betta Edu, paid only 1 out of 9 months owed in December 2023. N-Power Programme benefits privileged class at the expense of majority. Elite’s misuse of public funds hinders socioeconomic progress.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Mixed research was adopted in this paper. The population of the study is a set of significant elements such as people, traits, events, organizations which are relevant to the situation of interest under study. Thus, the projected population of 44,112,908 was used for this paper. This report is based on the statistical research jointly conducted by the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) and the National Population Commission (NPC) in 2019. The sample size of 400 for this study was determined using Taro Yamane technique for sample size determination. The instruments for the data collection include the questionnaire and interview. Data was analysed using simple percentages.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Research Question: *How has N-Power Programme promoted human capital development and capacity building among beneficiaries in the Niger Delta?*

Table 1: Computation of percentage response of how N-Power Programme promote human capital development and capacity building among beneficiaries in the Niger Delta.

Questionnaires	Gender	SA	A	D	SD	Total
		f (%)	f (%)	f (%)	f (%)	
The N-Power programme has provided skills and enhances the initiatives of some beneficiaries in socioeconomic development.	Male	80	60	20	30	190
		21%	15%	5%	8%	49%
	Female	120	40	30	10	200
		31%	10%	8%	2%	51%
	Total	200	100	50	40	390
		51%	25%	12%	10%	100%
The programme has increased the level of income thereby improving the standard of living through enhanced capacity building.	Male	90	60	10	30	190
		23%	28%	8%	18%	49%
	Female	90	50	20	40	200
		23%	13%	5%	10%	51%
	Total	180	110	30	70	390
		46%	43%	12%	28%	100%
The N-Power programme has encouraged beneficiaries to imbibe the culture of saving from stipends and allowances to enhance their skills.	Male	60	90	35	5	190
		15%	24%	9%	1%	49%
	Female	70	120	10	0	200
		18%	31%	2%	0%	51%
	Total	130	210	45	5	390
		61%	55%	11%	1	100%
The programme has improved the quality of life by boosting their confidence to be self-reliance in productive assets in socioeconomic development.	Male	60	100	5	25	190
		15%	26%	1%	7%	49%
	Female	100	95	5	0	200
		26%	24%	1%	0%	51%
	Total	160	195	10	25	390
		41%	50%	2%	7%	100%
N-Power programme has opened a door of social interaction amongst beneficiaries in areas of small businesses and employment creation in socioeconomic development.	Male	65	95	15	15	190
		17%	24%	4%	4%	49%
	Female	70	105	15	10	200
		18%	27%	4%	2%	51%
	Total	135	200	30	25	390
		35%	51%	8%	6%	100%

Source: Field Work, 2024.

Table 1 shows the views of respondents on how has N-Power programme improved the standard of living and quality of life for the residents of the Niger Delta.

In their view on whether N-Power programme has provided skills and enhances the initiatives of some beneficiaries in socioeconomic development, the table shows that 200 respondents which represent 51% of the 390 respondents strongly agreed with 100 respondents representing 26% agreed that N-Power programme has provided skills and enhances the initiatives of some beneficiaries in socioeconomic development. However, 50 (13%) “disagreed” while 40 (10%) “strongly disagreed” that N-Power programme has provided skills and enhances the initiatives of some beneficiaries in socioeconomic development. This infers that N-Power programme has provided skills and enhances the initiatives of some beneficiaries in socioeconomic development.

The table also reveals that 180 (46%) and 110 (28%) respondents confirmed to “strongly agreed” and “agreed” that programme has increased the level of income thereby improving the standard of living and quality of life while enhancing socioeconomic development. 30 respondents which represents 8% disagreed with 70 respondents representing 18% strongly disagreed with the claim that the programme has increased the level of income thereby improving the standard of living and quality of life while enhancing socioeconomic development. It indicates that the programme has increased the level of income thereby improving the standard of living and quality of life while enhancing socioeconomic development.

On whether the N-Power programme has encouraged beneficiaries to imbibe the culture of saving from stipends and allowances to enhance the standard of living and quality of life, 130 (33%) respondents strongly agreed, with 210 respondents representing 54% agreed that the N-Power programme has encouraged beneficiaries to imbibe the culture of saving from stipends and allowances to enhance the standard of living and quality of life. While 45 respondents represent 12% disagreed with 5 respondents representing 1% strongly disagreed. This implies that the N-Power programme has encouraged beneficiaries to imbibe the culture of saving from stipends and allowances to enhance the standard of living and quality of life.

On whether the programme has improved the quality of life by boosting their confidence to be self-reliance in productive assets in socioeconomic development, the table above shows that 160 (42%) respondents strongly agreed and 195 (50%) agreed that the programme has improved the quality of life by boosting their confidence to be self-reliance in productive assets in socioeconomic development. 10 representing 2% and 25 representing 6% of the respondents state that the programme has improved the quality of life by boosting their confidence to be self-reliance in productive assets in socioeconomic development. This implies that the programme has improved the quality of life by boosting their confidence to be self-reliance in productive assets in socioeconomic development.

The question of whether N-Power programme has opened a door of social interaction amongst beneficiaries in areas of small businesses and employment creation in socioeconomic development, the table above also displays 190 which represents 49% “strongly agreed” and 175 respondents representing 45% “agreed” that N-Power programme has opened a door of social interaction amongst beneficiaries in areas of small businesses and employment creation in socioeconomic development. 5 respondents with 1% disagreed while 20 respondents which represent 5% strongly disagreed on N-Power programme has opened a door of social interaction amongst beneficiaries in areas of small businesses and employment creation in socioeconomic development. The majority of the respondents strongly agreed that N-Power programme has opened a door of social interaction amongst beneficiaries in areas of small businesses and employment creation in socioeconomic development.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The Role of the N-Power Programme in Promoting Human Capital Development and Capacity Building among Beneficiaries in the Niger Delta: The study revealed that N-Power programme has provided skills and enhances the initiatives of some beneficiaries in socioeconomic development, the table shows that 200 respondents which represent 51% of the 390 respondents strongly agreed with 100 respondents representing 26% agreed that N-Power programme has provided skills and enhances the initiatives of some beneficiaries in socioeconomic development. However, 50 (13%) “disagreed” while 40 (10%) “strongly disagreed” that N-Power programme has provided skills and enhances the

initiatives of some beneficiaries in socio-economic development. This infers that N-Power programme has provided skills and enhances the initiatives of some beneficiaries in socio-economic development. 180 (46%) and 110 (28%) respondents also confirmed to “strongly agreed” and “agreed” that programme has increased the level of income thereby improving the standard of living and quality of life while enhancing socioeconomic development. 30 respondents which represents 8% disagreed with 70 respondents representing 18% strongly disagreed with the claim that the programme has increased the level of income thereby improving the standard of living and quality of life while enhancing socioeconomic development. It indicates that the programme has increased the level of income thereby improving the standard of living and quality of life while enhancing socioeconomic development. On whether the N-Power programme has encouraged beneficiaries to imbibe the culture of saving from stipends and allowances to enhance the standard of living and quality of life, 130 (33%) respondents strongly agreed, with 210 respondents representing 54% agreed that the N-Power programme has encouraged beneficiaries to imbibe the culture of saving from stipends and allowances to enhance the standard of living and quality of life. While 45 respondents represent 12% disagreed with 5 respondents representing 1% strongly disagreed. This implies that the N-Power programme has encouraged beneficiaries to imbibe the culture of saving from stipends and allowances to enhance the standard of living and quality of life. On whether the programme has improved the quality of life by boosting their confidence to be self-reliance in productive assets in socioeconomic development, the table above shows that 160 (42%) respondents strongly agreed and 195 (50%) agreed that the programme has improved the quality of life by boosting their confidence to be self-reliance in productive assets in socioeconomic development. 10 representing 2% and 25 representing 6% of the respondents state that the programme has improved the quality of life by boosting their confidence to be self-reliance in productive assets in socioeconomic development. This implies that the programme has improved the quality of life by boosting their confidence to be self-reliance in productive assets in socioeconomic development. The question of whether N-Power programme has opened a door of social interaction amongst beneficiaries in areas of small businesses and employment creation in socioeconomic development, the table above also displays 190 which represents 49% “strongly agreed” and 175 respondents representing 45% “agreed” that N-Power programme has opened a door of social interaction amongst beneficiaries in areas of small businesses and employment creation in socioeconomic development. 5 respondents with 1% disagreed while 20 respondents which represent 5% strongly disagreed on N-Power programme has opened a door of social interaction amongst beneficiaries in areas of small businesses and employment creation in socioeconomic development. The majority of the respondents strongly agreed that N-Power programme has opened a door of social interaction amongst beneficiaries in areas of small businesses and employment creation in socioeconomic development. This is consistent with the claims made by Salami (2013) that the literacy rate is a key factor in the explanation of national progress. He opined that formal education is a reliable means to empower the youths while skill acquisition is a better means to empower youths against unemployment. Secondly, 90% of the respondents affirmed that N-Power is concerned with the empowerment of the youths and ensure that stipends and allowances are paid to youths as an effective way to enhance their skills. This is in tandem with the view of Eluemunor (2018) who emphasized that:

The N-Power programme focuses on helping young people realize their values in a compassionate society and on getting society to recognize the benefit of investing in youth. Also, there is no government that have establish skill network for the unemployed youths (p.34).

Responding to the above, Ugiagbe (2011) opined that giving the youths and young graduates access to socioeconomic resources enhances their performances. Dauda (2017) asserted that involving young people in decision-making processes and encouraging them to take an active role in socioeconomic development issues can help them feel more in control of their lives. He believed that poverty is a major challenge to youth empowerment which is in line with the report of that social problem emanates from the inequitable distribution of power and resources. Omorogiuwa (2020) claimed that if the youths are empowered, they will view themselves useful and relevant to the economic

development of the region. Others would also perceive them from a position of strength and positivity, and that they will be seen as resources, experts in their own development, with capacities and potential, and as having abilities to make meaningful contributions rather than being perceived as problematic that need to be eliminated.

According to Anyebe (2018), there is strong empirical evidence that employment creation generally increases incomes and reduces poverty in low-income countries at both micro and macro levels, and a significant body of research decomposes the effect of various factors on poverty. Therefore, the government has given due consideration to youth in socio-economic and political development, the focus therefore, is to generate maximum expression of youthful creativity, productivity, ingenuity and freedom in the context of an appropriate environment for self-expression, self-sustenance and self-actualization and empowerment by the youth (Ijere, 2014). The linkages among education, poverty, unemployment, income inequality and economic growth in an economy have been discussed in many studies. According to Orokpo *et al* (1998), there is a significant impact on the youth's livelihood in terms of ownership of commercial vehicles, motor-cycles, bicycles, clothing, food crops and food consumption as a result of their participation in the programme. Similarly, Abbas (2013) states that the previously unemployed youths were able to secure a better level of living as a result of their participation in N-Power empowerment scheme. He further showed that access to poverty alleviation programmes improved socio-economic status of youths and promote their economic independence.

Aligning with the views of the above author, one of the respondents revealed that:

the N-Power programme has enabled to acquire a skill in masonry and this skill has provided me with all I need to know; in the aspect of building and construction material, the prices, the charges and profit. I have an in-depth knowledge about the skill and this is what I use to pay my rent and feed my family. N-Power has done well for me and I can now generate income for myself and family (P. Tamunokuro, personal communication, May 7, 2024).

The view of the respondent is confirmed when Abubakar (2020) averred that income generation is the process used to describe an investment or business activity that makes money through skills utilization, this is about ensuring the most effective application of skills in the work place to maximize performance through the interplay of a number of key agents (e.g. employers, employees, learning providers and the state) and the use of a range of human resource, management and working practices. He opined that income can be generated by self-employment, by working for others or by adding to personal resources through investment. The scholar stressed that on contribution of skills acquisition centres to poverty alleviation in the Niger Delta, it has helped in the alleviation of poverty by increasing participant income generation while in a similar vein, Michel and Nathan (2013) conducted a study on impact of poverty alleviation programmes on economic growth and income generation and revealed that the success of poverty alleviation on income generation among youths has enhanced their income and empowered them. Similarly, Ibietan and Ekhosuehi (2015) described as remarkable and significant the impact of N-Power on the income and standard of living of participants in Nigeria. The mean income of N-Power participants increased by 150 per cent after the intervention. In realization of the above, efforts of successive governments were geared towards provision of effective youth's empowerment schemes aimed at job creation to enhance income generation among the people. This empowerment scheme has adopted an approach to poverty alleviation based on recent understanding that livelihood strategies centred not only on the use of a range of natural, material and economic resources, but also social and cultural resources as empowerment tools. In line with the response of a scholars above, a respondent revealed that:

The government has over the years been developing and implementing various project and programmes in its development rolling plans and budget aimed at meeting the needs of citizenry to reducing poverty. The N-Power programme has provided functional healthcare services, job creation, boost agricultural services to equally reduce the unemployment rate and wide spread poverty in the Niger Delta region (E. Obule, personal communication, June 10, 2024)

Wangmo (2012) contended that the effects of unemployment on the psychological perspective of the society were very overwhelming to anyone who experienced them. Thus, the feeling of rejection and personal failure in them can only be imagined. The respondents blamed themselves for not being able to provide for themselves financially as a result of unemployment; they experienced feelings of guilt and had to rely on the financial support of others. They were forced to withdraw themselves from social interactions and isolated themselves from social activities as they were uncomfortable as unemployed youths. Broadly speaking, the frustration that stares every youth in the face is coming against the background that Nigeria is ranked as the sixth biggest producer of oil in the world and also a leading producer of natural gas, yet youth unemployment pervades the land. Evidently, the consequences of unemployment are not short lived; rather they create a sudden disorder in the society, prolonging a long-term effect. The impact of this according to Ugiagbe (2011) will be felt rather with a ripple effect with very negligible start at one point, eventually loading with an extensive impact to the society, then to the nation and the globe in the long run. As a result, the Nigerian society has become very unsafe for youths to find meaningful employment. It was reported that about one hundred business organizations folded up in Nigeria due to unfriendly nature of the environment (Edokpolor and Owenvbiugie, 2017). Data gathered from the second hypothesis revealed that there was a significant relationship between youth unemployment and their involvement in criminal activities.

Obviously, an interviewee responded that:

The lingering unemployment among the youths was fast tearing the fabric of society, thereby turning the youths who should have been agents of development into armed robbery so as to earn a living. However, the N-Power programme to a larger extent has provided the skills to bridge the wider gap. Youths are gradually seeing the usefulness of the N-Power programme in the Niger Delta despite some hiccups in the programme (N. Worlu, personal communication, June 14, 2024).

Drew from above, it is germane to state that the N-Power programme has reduce the increasing rate of armed robbery and other social vices due to the growing unemployment rate in the Niger Delta. The gigantic task of N-Power to reduce unemployment is beyond the singular capability of the government but requires the patriotic intervention of all stakeholders and well-meaning Nigerians. Poverty and idleness are borne out of youth unemployment and the architect of deprivation and underdevelopment that virtually tends to breed crime of all form including armed robbery. According to Seabi (2009), youth unemployment has increased the level of social insecurity in the country. Violence can affect any member of a family and socioeconomic. It could be in a socioeconomic and within the family. Unemployment undermines traditional bases of masculinity resulting in males committing violence within the family as well as outside home as an alternative marker of their masculinity. He stressed that since the unemployed see themselves as outsiders of their society because they perceived as second-class citizens, any act of violence engineered by them could affect any member of a family and socioeconomic. In addition, they feel socially isolated and marginalized by society, and believe that they are stigmatized by society (Thaler, 2010). Unemployment, which is seen as one of those problems that fuels social unrest in various communities and towns, is caused by the high escalating rate of unemployment in such places (Jili, 2012). When people cannot achieve their goals because they have been prevented by circumstances beyond their control, they become frustrated. It is important to stress that frustration does not necessarily lead directly to aggression, but rather to rage (sentiment). Since the frustration is unexpected, more resentment which could then lead to releasing aggression on people or objects such as weaker people, animals and buildings to relieve themselves of their frustration begins to manifest. The inability to fulfil their basic needs leads to intense frustration and protest against government in power. This form of protest, regarded as socio-economic phenomenon is driven by the frustrations of poverty and inequality, and has become increasingly violent in recent times. Some of the respondents concurred that the participation of youths in political activities and leadership enhances socioeconomic development. This also is in accordance to the view of the Eluemunor (2018) who argued that youth participation gives young

people a voice by allowing them to shape the trajectory of their development through actively shaping processes, collective decisions, and outcomes in pursuit of justice, exposing abuses of power, and realizing their rights.

Another respondent revealed that:

Youth participation in N-Power programme has improve the socioeconomic lives of the people in the region. The youths need to be at the helm of affairs to positively influence socioeconomic development. Utilizing one's individual and communal strengths will result in a direct process of change. Youths are agents of change in socioeconomic development activities. N-Power has exposed me to and how to manage socioeconomic development issues making me experienced in the field (C. Tamuno, personal communication, May 17, 2024).

This is in line with the positive youth development idea enunciated by N-Power which focuses on young people's abilities, potential for development, and increasingly good behaviours rather than their flaws. The report above shows that if the youths are empowered, they can influence positive change and development in socioeconomic development. Thus, focus is on the strengths of the youths and not their weaknesses.

In line with the extent N-Power programme has improved the standard of living and quality of lives in the Niger Delta as discussed above, Nwagu (n.d) have also contributed to the literatures as follow:

Agriculture remains the largest economic sector in many developing countries. It could be a significant generator of employment, contributing to poverty reduction and food scarcity. It is unfortunate to note that the ability of Nigeria to harness the growth potential of the agricultural sector can be retarded. Improvement in agricultural productivity and innovation can be a driver in economic development. The view of Nwagu is a testament to the foregoing that N-Power is a beautiful programme aimed at reducing poverty through a very robust agricultural policy to reduce unemployment and generate income. Many respondents have testified to the views above. Some revealed how they were deployed to agricultural research centres to boost agricultural produces and increase food productivity. Others revealed to the extent on how their knowledge have been improved by the introduction of the N-Power programme. They further stressed the importance of this programme to their socioeconomic development and recommended it for a continuous future Niger Deltans and Nigerians. Another area mentioned by Nwagu is sustainable socioeconomic development. He opined that it involves continuous improvement in the well-being and the standard of living of the people, which could be summarized in terms of income, health, education, environment, and freedoms. For the first three of these, per capita income, life expectancy at birth, infant mortality, and adult literacy are the proxies to be measured and compared. In other words, sustainable socioeconomic development is a process, which manages to combine the social, economic, and environmental aspects of development and establish a close link between these three pillars. He noted that good governance, which is about appropriation, participation, responsiveness, accountability and sustainability is required to drive home socioeconomic development of the people. It constitutes the above link and one of the preconditions for sustainable socioeconomic development. Going by the words of Nwagu above, the N-Power programme is established by the government to improve on the standard of living, enhance quality of lives and exert socioeconomic conditions for the generality of the people. The programme takes a gradual process to cover aspects of health, agriculture, technological support, building construction, skill acquisition, leadership development, educational expertise, etc. The purpose is to develop and transform the minds of the people to agree with developmental programmes directed towards socioeconomic sustainability. Be that as it may, the N-Power programme is a continuity that is capable of addressing the needs of the people but not in a hurry or short time. The scholar also noted that the right conditions and institutional frameworks upon which to encourage investment, innovation, and economic development need to be created. Capacity to ensure sound, transparent financial and economic management must be built while public policies that encourage private investment and reduce corruption must be enforced to the latter (Awofeso & Irabor, 2020). This requires strong institutions and balanced laws as well as fair and effective regulatory regimes to oversee competition, the maintenance of standards, resource management, and

property rights in the governing of the economy. Fair and equitable labour codes and laws will serve as empowerment to disadvantaged people in particular to ensure their engagement in the formal economy. This will enable them to have access to land and resources, security of tenure, and the capacity to make use of their assets in a more productive and sustainable manner. Government policies that open markets to trade and infrastructure investments are also required.

The private sector remains a driving force behind any sustainable economic development (Adams, 2023). He opines that the higher levels of growth and poverty reduction can be achieved in Nigeria giving the presence of a robust private sector. Sustainable socioeconomic development can be stimulated by enhancing the productivity and competitiveness of enterprises so as to generate new formal employment opportunities. Nigeria should identify a few clusters which have the potential to grow and develop a comprehensive approach to encouraging the clusters to thrive. This will help to overcome constraints faced by entrepreneurs, especially female entrepreneurs. Access to legitimate credit and financial services need to be increased. Sustainable economic development requires sustainable enterprises. It requires a new way of doing business. It requires business enterprises to take steps to become greener in their operations as well as new and clean environmental technologies, with some companies specializing in their production while others are engaged in making use of such production (Alfa, Otaida & Audu, 2014). A new way of doing business is emerging out of this transformation. A new way of economic life that will empower Nigerians to meet their needs and still be able to conserve the earth and its resources for present and future generations is needed. One of the engines of transformation is green industries. The green industry is depicted in resource efficiency, pollution prevention, recycling, the minimization of waste, renewable energy transformation etc.

Nwagu noted that environmental sustainability means maintenance of socioeconomic indices/factors in a dynamic environment. He stressed that economic sustainability forms an important component of sustainable development. The government must constantly adopt developmental programmes tailored towards the sustainability of the socioeconomic development. Sustainability is the maintenance and sustenance of a high real growth rate of the economy to achieve the development or economic objectives. The N-Power programme is a veritable tool that the government has leverage upon over the last eight years to manage socioeconomic issues of vulnerable and people living in poverty.

Some achievements have been recorded by the N-Power poverty reduction programme such as huge resources voted by the government to enhance socioeconomic development of the people of the Niger Delta in the areas of food production, agricultural extension services, primary health care, and education enrolment. Also, the study found that the N-Power programme has provided skills and enhances the initiatives of some beneficiaries in socio-economic development. The N-Power programme has increased the level of income thereby improving the standard of living and quality of life while enhancing socioeconomic development. It has improved the quality of life by boosting their confidence to be self-reliance in productive assets in socioeconomic development. It has also opened doors of social interaction amongst beneficiaries in areas of small businesses and employment creation in socioeconomic development. However, the fact that the incidence of poverty remains very high, the existence of the various programmes notwithstanding, points to the ineffectiveness of the strategies and the programmes. There is still public outcry that much has not been achieved, as the schemes are usually said to be hijacked by politicians and their associates, friends and family, thus rendering it ineffective as most of the deserving beneficiaries are excluded from the schemes.

CONCLUSION

The paper concludes that the N-Power programme has a significant relationship with poverty reduction. It also has a significant relationship with socioeconomic development outcomes in the Niger Delta even if it is weak. The relationships are demonstrated in the discussion of findings where beneficiaries revealed that the N-Power programme has enhanced their teaching or educational skills, healthcare practitioners, skill acquisition, technological enhancement, and to poverty reduction. The paper has also revealed that the programme has increased the level of income thereby improving the standard of living and quality of life, provided skills and enhances the initiatives of some beneficiaries. It has also opened doors of social interaction amongst beneficiaries in areas of small businesses and employment creation. However, the paper also revealed that socioeconomic development programmes were not properly coordinated by N-Power officials and the Ministry of

Humanitarian Affairs and Poverty Alleviation due to several factors such as poor application and pattern of implementation of poverty alleviation scheme, inadequate funding of the N-Power scheme to reducing poverty, excessive political interest, irregular payment of stipends and allowances, poor monitoring and coordination, bribery in the PPAs of volunteers, mismanagement and embezzlement of fund, lack of transparency, poor performance of government officials and absence of stakeholders and beneficiaries' involvement in N-Power poverty alleviation programme are definite keys to the success or failure of the programme. These factors undermine the impact of N-Power programme in poverty reduction and socioeconomic development in the Niger Delta region. In a nutshell, the study concludes that there exists significant relationship between the N-Power programme and poverty reduction as well as N-Power programme and socioeconomic development in the Niger Delta region but the relationships appear to be weak.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on our findings, the study recommends the following:

- i. State and local governments should provide accurate data of those living in poverty while the federal government coordinate, oversee and monitor poverty alleviation programmes in the Niger Delta region. The effort to alleviate poverty should not be left in the hands of the federal government alone. States and local governments should be involved while playing relevant roles in reducing poverty in their respective domain or jurisdictions. Adequate poverty reduction measures that involve the people would help to address and reduce the high crime rates and economic sabotage frequently experienced in the Niger Delta area.
- ii. The federal government should establish more skill development centres where human capital development and capacity building become very essential for young graduates. The government should also demonstrate the political will and sincerity in the fight against corruption, administrative highhandedness, inordinate ambition of N-Power officials to amass wealth, and political greed inherent in the management of the N-Power scheme and ensure that volunteers are paid regularly without delay and other factors that seek to impede the programme to enable them feel the impact of socioeconomic relevance. Regular payment of stipends and allowances would enable beneficiaries to save and create new avenues to establish small businesses through human development skills and capacity building.
- iii. The federal government should engage the services of policy experts, anti-graft agents and external auditors to assess the effectiveness of the performance of the N-Power Programme on a quarterly basis in the Niger Delta. These experts should go for on-the site assessment or visit areas of deployment of volunteers in order to produce the needed results. The collaborative services of these experts would determine the extent of effectiveness of the programme while enhancing policy implementation to reducing mismanagement of fund, bribery of officials of the programme, lack of transparency, and excessive political interest.

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